

SPELLING PROFICIENCY LEVEL OF TEACHER EDUCATION STUDENTS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 25

Issue 8

Pages: 991-1005

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2407

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13837775

Manuscript Accepted: 08-23-2024

Spelling Proficiency Level of Teacher Education Students

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Abstract

This study determined the relationship of socio-demographic profile, social media platforms and spelling proficiency level among Teacher Education students in Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception Baybay Leyte Incorporated. The spelling proficiency level is categorized into Independent/Mastery, Instructional and Frustration level. A personally-designed survey questionnaire and interview sheet were utilized to gather the needed data from 174 Teacher Education students. Percentage, frequency count, weighted mean, Chi-square test, T-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were utilized. Results revealed that most of the respondents come from families of Class E socio-economic classification, but still has access to gadgets. The spelling proficiency level of most of the respondents belong to Frustration Level with the mean percentage of 60.17%. From 100 words, 32 words were commonly misspelled which means 100 respondents and above misspelled these words. Significant relationship in terms of FB & Instagram Users, Age and Proficiency Level and FB, Twitter & Instagram Users and Occupation of Mother were revealed. Results also show that there is a high significant relationship among FB, Twitter & Instagram Users, Age and Proficiency Level. A proposed module is designed to enhance the spelling skill proficiency level of the Teacher Education students.

Keywords: *spelling proficiency, education students, social media influence, frustration level*

Introduction

Today, educators are faced with the challenge of addressing the needs of the growing number of students whose primary language is not English (Gibbons, 2003 as cited by Vizconde, 2006). Magbanua (2016) asserts that the need to be proficient in the use of English among non-native speakers has become a global phenomenon. While mastering other skills and content in other subject areas, there is the necessity for these learners to gain proficiency in English.

In the past years, students are more exposed to the internet and the social media platforms due to its easier access which become the greatest competitor for the teachers. Aaron Smith and Monica Anderson (2018) assert that the social media landscape is a mix of long-standing trends and newly emerging narratives. Facebook and YouTube dominate this landscape, as notable majorities of U.S. adults use each of these sites. At the same time, younger teens (especially those ages 18 to 24) stand out for embracing a variety of platforms and using them frequently. Some 78% of 18 to 24 year olds use Snapchat, and a sizeable majority of these users (71%) visit the platform multiple times per day. Similarly, 71% of Americans in this age group now use Instagram and close to half (45%) are Twitter users.

The Filipinos are adept in using any social media platforms. This is proven by Miguel Camus (2018), as the Philippines topped the world in terms of social media usage as the number of internet users in the country hit 67 million people.

The generation now has been labeled as the millennials and many studies show that technology is already part of their daily living. While it is true that social media is playing a great role to connect people, it could also influence their language acquisition thus affecting student's spelling proficiency.

Nicole Marie Dilts (2000) states that errors of students are on spelling amongst grammar, paragraph structure and formality. She further contends that this may be caused by students using words which they are not familiar with in their formal papers because this engagement in media pertains only to basic and common words used daily.

Enhancing the teaching of English in the Philippines presents opportunities for the country in the area of tourism. Cabigon (2015) quoted the chief of the ESL Market Development Group under the Department of Tourism, Renee Marie Reyes' words, "To maintain the Philippines' strength as a major ESL destination, we need to address the gap in qualified ESL teachers and the issues around ensuring the quality of ESL schools. This also includes exploring how we can extend incentives to ESL schools and teachers."

Representatives of the academe focused on teacher training and professional development, highlighting the need for skills in differentiated instruction, materials development and knowledge sharing. According to its dean, Rosario Alonzo, the University of the Philippines College of Education ensures this by emphasizing to its students that English is a skill to be used for communication. Education students focus on learner-centered teaching, and are taught to ask learners to do meaningful tasks using English. Future teachers should ensure that English is a means of communication, rather than a set of facts to be learned. In the same way, the Department of Education focuses on the needs of learners and ensures that they learn the English language holistically, as specified under the K-to-12 basic education framework.

Among college students of Franciscan College of Immaculate Conception Baybay Leyte Incorporated, the researcher observed in her

classes that spelling proficiency is a common problem. Students used the spelling of your or you're to UR, you to U and are as R, and many more.

It is on these premises that the study is made to determine the students' spelling skill proficiency level and ascertain its relationship to their frequent social media use. The difficulties and common errors in spelling are recognized, being the basis for designing a module with the purpose of developing the level of mastery in the student's spelling proficiency.

This study will benefit the school administration and staff especially the faculty in addressing spelling problems of students. The result of this study will serve as a model for English teachers to determine appropriate strategies that would motivate and hold interest of the students, thus making learning an enjoyable experience for them. For the students, the outcome shall make them appreciate the values and importance of learning the English grammar focusing on their spelling skills competency and make them consider and apply these in their future lives.

In this study, the researcher aims to contribute to Psychology and Education by determining spelling skill proficiency level of Teacher Education students of Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception Baybay Leyte Incorporated and to design an intervention program that will enhance their spelling proficiency.

Research Questions

This study determined the relationship of social media platforms and spelling proficiency level among Teacher Education students in Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception Baybay Leyte Incorporated. Specifically, the study answered the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. Age;
 - 1.2. Sex;
 - 1.3. Family Income;
 - 1.4. Parents' Occupation; and
 - 1.5. Previous School Attended?
2. What are the various social media platforms that the students use?
3. How often do students use these social media platforms?
4. What is the spelling skill proficiency level of the students?
5. What are the common errors in spelling?
6. Is there a significant relationship among socio-demographic profile, media use and spelling proficiency level?
7. What proposed module can be designed to enhance spelling skill proficiency level of the students?

Literature Review

Social Media Platforms

The Internet era changed the information world with regard to sharing, speed, storage and information acquisition in whatever form regardless of the person's location. Through the Internet, a number of web technologies emerged, and one technology that is making waves with regard to information sharing and communication is the social media platforms.

The evolution of social media has cut across all aspects of society with its positive and negative influences. Social media has transformed and impacted on communication, learning, research and education in general.

Maina (2018) lists the popular social media platforms around the globe. It shows that Facebook is the biggest social media network on the Internet, both in terms of total number of users and name recognition. This automatically makes it one of the best medium for connecting people from all over the world with your business. Businesses can also use Twitter to interact with prospective clients, answer questions, release latest news and at the same time use the targeted ads with specific audiences. LinkedIn is hands-down the most popular social media site for professional networking. The website is available in 24 languages and has over 400 million registered users. LinkedIn is great for people looking to connect with people in similar industries, networking with local professionals and displaying business related information and statistics. Instagram is a visual social media platform. Many of its users use it to post information about travel, fashion, food, art and similar subjects. The platform is also distinguished by its unique filters together with video and photo editing features. Snapchat is an image messaging application software product that was created by Reggie Brown, Evan Spiegel and Bobby Murphy when they were students at Stanford University.

Being involved in social media is one of the most active web-based activities in the Philippines. Because of this, Filipinos are declared to be the most active users on a number of web-based social network sites, such as Facebook, Instagram, Snapchat and Twitter. This is proven by The House of IT (2018) that the use of social networking websites has become so extensive that the country is now called "The Social Networking Capital of the World." The total population in the Philippines has reached over 100 million – and 46% of the population are active Internet users. Almost all Filipinos are actively joining social media, not just to connect with friends and family but also for the purpose of catching news, purchasing products and services, and even job searching.

Chagas (2016) insists on particular sensibility of communication and information technologies to the social uses of these technologies, as well as to their effects. He further asserts that traditionalists believe that network society and its associated technology does not constitute an independent strength that destroys everything which previously had any human touch.

Current research of EDUCAUSE Center for Analysis and Research (2018) suggests that in the higher education setting, social media may be used to improve communication between students, instructors, and the surrounding campus community. While many different types of communication tools are available in the learning setting, the advantage of using popular social media platforms is that most students arrive to campus as fluent users of these virtual tools. Whether or not instructors adopt social media as an education tool, chances are their students already have created a class-specific Facebook group, use Twitter to share course information, or use another social media platform to communicate with other students outside of class.

Advances in technology have resulted in an increase in the number of internet users among students. They use social networks for different aims. The Internet as a means of advanced technology has had a huge impact on the English language in less than two decades changing it to a considerable extent. The main reason for this is the efficiency of the internet communication and easy accessibility of the world-wide net. In this note, many researches have been implemented to find out how it influences students' language. Social media usage by students is so rampant because of easily access to devices such as smart phones, iPhone, tablets, iPad and laptops which are connected to the internet.

Texting through SNSs improves students' literacy and vocabulary enlargement. This is in line with David Crystal's (2008) conclusion that it provides more opportunities to engage with the language. However, Craig (2003) disproves that texting threatens students' literacy because it creates undesirable reading and writing habits due to common use of abbreviations and unusual jargon, thereby damaging students' ability to employ formal literacy skills.

Spelling Skill Proficiency Level

Spelling is a conservative measure of students' knowledge about words and if a learner can spell a word, decoding the word is evident. Spelling proficiency is to recognize and spell a word right and learners must be able to distinguish between the different sounds a word makes when it is pronounced. Lanir (2011) defines spelling or orthography, as a neurologically demanding sub-skill of writing, involving a range of linguistic skills. Spelling proficiency requires the acquisition of phonological knowledge, morphological awareness, and orthographic rules. So, in order to spell, learners need to have control over the sounds and structure of a language and its spelling system. Kamhi and Hinton (2000) even implied that the historically dismissive attitude of psycholinguists toward spelling is changing, and many researchers are beginning to recognize spelling as a complex multifaceted skill and are paying more attention to the cognitive processes involved in acquiring it.

Furthermore, Chandler (2000) stresses that good spelling is a necessary skill for both higher education and the workplace. Jayousi (2011) emphasizes that spelling difficulties cause learners to commit many spelling errors that distort their written production, affecting negatively their overall writing proficiency. With this, Smith (2015) concludes that it forms an integral part of the academic achievement.

Teachers may assume that once their students have mastered the spelling of most of the common English words, they will refrain from making errors in the future. Studies say that reading misspelled words can destabilize memories of correct word forms, creating confusion and regression in a student's spelling ability. Spelling acquisition are best accounted for by the various models and strategies and that learning to read and write has a profound effect on the phonological knowledge of an adult literate speaker. Porter (2003) justifies that students judged spelling to be important and felt that spelling instruction during high school was insufficient. Teachers also judged spelling to be important and in need of increased attention during high school.

Traditionally, the procedure used to teach spelling in most language arts classes was to assign students to memorize a weekly list of words, then to administer a pretest and a final test to assess their word knowledge. Consequently, Block (2001) emphasizes that both the philosophy and strategies of teaching spelling began to change. Recently, with the K to 12 curriculum, Fry (2008) accentuates that it offers a teacher-developed curriculum that can help students develop strong spelling and word recognition skills, and reinforces strong reading development. This is a comprehensive spelling program that extends past the simple memorization of the letters that make up the individual words. With Anderson (2008), a teacher makes efforts to gain an understanding of students' prerequisite knowledge, including any misconceptions that the learner starts with in their construction of new knowledge. Given the importance of spelling proficiency to academic success, researchers and educators must determine the most efficient and effective methods to teach spelling.

Technology has been developing many automated spelling checkers and softwares like Grammarly, Unichck, Ludwig.guru, Ginger, SlickWrite and many others which automatically shifts to the proper spelling and correct grammar usage. And with this, the importance of spelling has been questioned in recent years, as word processing programs are equipped with spell checkers, and some educational reformists have suggested that focusing on spelling holds back the creative processes of writing and that students will naturally develop spelling skills through reading. Reading Specialist Susan Jones (2010) emphasizes that learning to spell helps to cement the connection between the letters and their sounds, and learning high-frequency "sight words" to mastery level improves both reading and writing. Technology is a powerful tool that can make learning easier. In the hands of the student with good language skills, the spell checker

is a real timesaver. However, it can actually interfere with the learning process. The writer must rely on starting the word correctly and getting most letters right, and the spell checker will not correct when a misspelling is another legitimate word. When a college student writes “lessening” instead of “listening,” that student has not learned to think about the relationship between the meaning and spelling of words. The student’s writing is suffering for the lack of accuracy, and perhaps reading skills as well.

In the academe, spelling proficiency seems to be a problem. Smith (2017) stresses that due to the focus on literacy and literacy levels in South Africa, the spelling proficiency of students have come under scrutiny, as educators exert an influence on the learners and their academic performance in class. Bosiwah (2015) highlights that the standard of English has been criticized as being low. The Chief Examiner’s Report on the 2001 - 2010 Basic Education Certificate Examination (B.E.C.E.) at the Central Region of Ghana singled out poor spelling as a major cause of the poor performance by candidates during examination. College students’ low English proficiency, which includes spelling, has received increasing attention in Taiwan these years. This is further stated by Hsu and Sheu (2008) that on 2000 and 2001, the Language Training and Testing Center (LTTC) involved 9,527 students from 85 technical colleges in Taiwan in a test equivalent to the General English Proficiency Test (GEPT) beginners’ level, a level junior high school graduates are supposed to reach. The result of the test indicated that, except in the department of foreign languages and of tourism, the percentage of college students who passed the test in all other departments did not exceed 20 %.

Philippines is recognized globally as one of the largest English-speaking nations with majority of its population having at least some degree of fluency in the language. Cabigon (2015) reports that English has always been one of the official languages of the Philippines and is spoken by more than 14 million Filipinos. It is the language of commerce and law, as well as the primary medium of instruction in education. Proficiency in the language is also one of the country’s strengths that has helped drive the economy and even made the Philippines the top voice outsourcing destination in the world, surpassing India in 2012. The influx of foreign learners of English is also on the rise due to the relatively more affordable but quality English as a Second Language (ESL) programs being offered locally. However, in a recent roundtable discussion organized by the British Council, key stakeholders from the government, academe, private, and non-government sectors acknowledged that even if the Philippines is doing fine in terms of English competency, concerns on how much of a competitive advantage it still is for the country were raised. The stakeholders agreed that the country needs to step up its efforts in improving the teaching and learning of English, developing it as a vital skill of the workforce. This is an initiative that could potentially strengthen the Philippines’ distinct advantage in this part of the world, particularly with the upcoming ASEAN economic integration.

With this, developing a working orthography is an area where teachers need the help of linguistics experts from the academe. Hernandez (2018) states that a vital prerequisite for developing educational materials in a local language is a working orthography that represent rules for using symbols. The need for developing the English proficiency- both oral and written communication, which then includes the spelling competency, is recognized by the government. Evidently, Bongato (2014) states that Former President Gloria Macapagal-Arroyo’s administration had its “National English Proficiency Program” that reportedly had a budget of Php500 million for training several thousand teachers nationwide.

Uy (2006) reports that seminars and workshops sponsored by DepEd and CHED have focused more on teaching strategies and language proficiency, leading to odd combination of better teaching techniques and substandard English language proficiency. At present, the DepEd has its “Language Competency Benchmark” as the official guideline for the standard competency requirements of all its personnel. The weakening of the direct linguistic connection with native English speakers has led to the situation of Filipinos learning English mainly from each other. Any new pronunciation, idiom, word usage, phrase structure, or even spelling generated by an adult, especially one who is looked up to by the society as a good exemplar of English, gets spread by diffusion.

This may be due to the use of social media among students. Funell (2017) expresses that digital tools made them more likely to ‘use poor spelling and grammar’.

This is supported by the English Spelling Society (2010) in Canada who concludes that the internet has revolutionized the English language, and made misspelling the norm. As people type at speed online, there is now a “general attitude” that there is no need to correct mistakes or conform to regular spelling rules, it says. But this means that children who have been brought up with the internet do not question wrongly spelt words. There is profundity of taking cognizance of the students’ spelling especially in the light of modern technology and social networking sites. With this, McMillan (2017) discloses that social media’s impact on language and communication, especially among younger generations, adds a new layer of complexity for teachers trying to relate to and understand their students.

Educators play a significant role in the student’s foundation of learning. Student educators are trained at the tertiary level and their language preparation to teach learners should incorporate a focus on proper spelling of educators as part of their training. However, Smith (2015) proves that student educators tend to overestimate their levels of spelling proficiency. The crucial focus of paying attention to spelling even at the university level, is the fact that student educators will be teaching the Foundation Phase of learners on how to spell once they are appointed as educators in the schools.

Reutzel and Cooter (2012) emphasize that quality educator knowledge directly impacts learner achievement, since the more the educator knows, the more equipped one can share correct information and spell correctly as part of literacy development. Society

values correct spelling, and spelling mistakes are often interpreted as a lack of diligence and mental effort. With that in view, Fellows and Oakley (2013) express that writers who know how to spell correctly are competent and good at communicating when using the written word. Good spelling is also linked inextricably with good reading. It goes to show that spelling is central to language development.

Even with the growing trend, there is little research to suggest social media is having an influence on students. Still, regardless of the true impact on an emerging issue, grammar remains a debatable topic. In recognizing the importance of writing well, education advocates are stressing the need to keep grammar lessons interesting and current. Thus, the researcher finds the necessity for such study on the relationship among the socio-demographic profile of the respondents, social media platforms and spelling skill proficiency level to fully understand and design a module that shall develop the student's spelling skills.

Methodology

Research Design

This study is a mixed method of quantitative and qualitative research aimed to determine the spelling skill proficiency level of the respondents and to ascertain its relationship to social media usage and the respondent's socio-demographic profile. Using the questionnaire employing the descriptive method, it enabled the researcher to describe the data and characteristics of social media and spelling skill proficiency level of the respondents. Moreover, it described the characteristics that were present with respect to variables in the situation. The italicized words in the discussion are in support to the qualitative data. An interview was also conducted after gathering the data from the respondents to analyze the implications and reasons of the data results.

Respondents

The study was conducted among the Education Students at Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception, Baybay Leyte Incorporated, Baybay City, Leyte. A pre-survey of the Part I and II of the questionnaire was used for 215 Education students that consist of BEED and BSED students specializing English, Math and Filipino to determine the qualified respondents. The result of the pre-survey determines the actual number of respondents which totals to 174 students.

Instrument

The survey questionnaire is personally designed and was subjected to a dry-run to determine its validity. Revisions were made and approval for the panel was sought. It has three parts.

Part I is the socio-demographic profile of the respondent in terms of age, sex, family income, parent's occupation, and previous school attended. Part II is the various social media platforms that the respondents use and the frequency usage basing on the hour spent per day. Part III is on the spelling skill proficiency level of the students with 100 words taken from various books used by Education students with the rating scale, adapted from Spinelli's Informal Spelling Inventory (2011), 90-100% as Independent/Mastery Level, 75-89% as Instructional Level, and below 75% as Frustration Level. The words selected were based on the consistency and the frequency of usage in the Teacher Education reference books.

A pre-survey of the first and second part of the research instrument was conducted to determine the final respondents of the study and only those who frequently use any social media platforms will be exposed to test on the spelling skill proficiency level.

Personally designed interview questions were also used as one of the research instruments after the conduct of the study to fully analyze the results of the gathered data.

Procedure

Upon the approval of the study by the panel, the researcher conducted a dry-run of the research instrument at Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception. Refinement and finalization of the instrument were done based on the result of the dry-run.

The researcher asked approval of the School Directress and the Dean of College for the conduct of the study. Once permitted, the questionnaires were distributed to the respondents. The data were collected and analyzed.

Data Analysis

The frequency, percentage and rank, were used to determine the frequent networking sites students use, time spent by the respondents and the socio-demographic profile. To ascertain the spelling skill proficiency level of the respondents, raw scores were computed to its percentage and mean.

The scale adapted from Spinelli's ISI was utilized in determining the spelling skill proficiency level with the following scale: Independent/ Mastery Level of 90%-100%, Instructional Level of 75% -89% and Frustration Level of below 75%.

To measure the common errors in the spelling, each response in the spelling recognition tests were tabulated and ranked from highest to lowest based on their percentage score hence, the basis for the designed module to enhance spelling skill proficiency.

To verify the significant relationship between social media use and spelling skill proficiency level, the data was treated using Chi-square test, T-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with the aid of a computer software.

For qualitative data, Thematic Analysis was used to generate codes from the interview transcripts.

Ethical Considerations

To address various concerns in preserving the privacy and security of the respondents, the researcher followed integrity and supported the Data Privacy Law and kept their identities and information discreet.

The researcher presented and discussed the informed consent and assent to the respondents before the conduct of the study to give them the freedom to decline their participation (see Appendix B & C). To assure them of their privacy, the researcher followed these steps: (1) distinguishing and coding of data; (2) no particular identifying information or mark in the survey questionnaire or the computer; (3) a secure storage for the data throughout the study; (4) destroying of information after use.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results based on the objectives of the study. It discusses and interprets the data gathered which were organized in accordance to the statistical tool used and treated to determine the significance of relationship between variables.

Socio-Demographic Profile Of Respondents

The socio-demographic profile of the respondents is one of the factors which affect the spelling proficiency of the students. The term "socio-demographic" refers to a group defined by its sociological and demographic characteristics. These characteristics are pertaining to, or characterized by a combination of sociological and demographic characteristics. In this study it is composed of 174 selected students taking the program of Teacher Education of the Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception (FCIC), Baybay Leyte Incorporated, during the academic year 2018-2019. The socio-demographic profile of the respondents include age, sex, annual family income, parents' occupation and previous school attended. Results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. *Distribution on the Socio-demographic Profile of Respondents*

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage (%)
A. Age N= 174		
16-20 yrs. old	83	48
21-25 yrs. old	70	40
26-30 yrs. old	13	7
31-35 yrs. old	5	3
36-45 yrs. old	3	2
B. Sex		
Male	56	32
Female	118	68
C. Annual Family Income		
Php 62,000-190,000	141	81
Php 191,000-602,000	18	10
Php 603, 000-1,856,000	4	3
Php 1,857,000- above	11	6
D. 1. Parents' Occupation (<i>Mother</i>)		
Housewife	94	54
Teacher	19	11
Deceased	17	10
Secretary/Clerk	10	6
Government Employee	11	6
OFW	5	3
Business	18	10
D. 2. Parents' Occupation (<i>Father</i>)		
Farmer	65	38
Laborer/Construction Worker	18	10
Caretaker	2	1
Sales Agent/Business	15	9
Deceased	14	8
Carpenter	8	5
Fisherman	5	3
Driver	18	10
Guard	2	1
Mechanic	6	3
None	9	5
Gov't Employee/ Official	9	5

Teacher	3	2
E. Previous School Attended		
Private	63	36
Public	111	64

Age. The results show that 83 (48%) respondents are 16-20 years old which falls within the normal age range of a college student in the Philippine Educational system. Most of the respondents were first year students who were pioneering in the K to 12 curriculum. Furthermore, results show that there are 3 (2%) respondents whose ages are 36-45 years old. During the interview, it was revealed that these respondents are those who started school late, repeated a grade level, and stopped going to school for some time either to take care of their family or find a job.

This is proven by Dale (2010) that while many students attend postsecondary institutions directly out of high school, they do not represent all college and university students. Some delay going on to college or university, while others may return for skills upgrading later in life or to pursue further postsecondary education.

Sex. In this study, the results exhibit that more than half (68%) of the respondents are female and only 56 (32%) are male respondents. It can be deduced that most of the college students taking the Teacher Education Program in FCIC are female. School teaching has long been associated with women. Ullah (2013) verifies that there has been an ideological link between women's domestic role and their career as school teacher. Taking care of younger children in school is traditionally seen as an "extension of motherhood" and therefore considered a "natural" job for women. This is also attested by Maurer (2017) that in 2014, women earned 80% of the Bachelor's degrees in Education, creating a female-dominated candidate pool for new teaching positions. Dee (2014) confirms that there is a gender gap growing in teaching profession.

Annual Family Income. Result indicates that 81% of the respondents have the annual income ranging from Php 62,000 to Php 190,000. This means that most of the students belong to Class E, according to the ABCDE socio-economic classification developed and proposed by Nielsen Admosphere. This result proves that most of the respondents belonged to low-income families, however, they still had access to smart phones and other gadgets which enables them to use social media platforms.

This is consistent with the study of Micheli (2016) on social networking sites (SNSs) which reveal that users' social background is not a significant predictor of participation in this type of social media. The broad user bases of Facebook and other social media platforms also appear to suggest that social background no longer affects access to SNSs.

Parent's Occupation. In table 1, results reveal that 94 (54%) respondents belong to a family where the mother is a housewife and 65 (38%) respondents' fathers are farmers. This indicates that it is accurate with the data regarding the annual family income which belongs to Class E.

The occupation of parents are significant factors that is considered in this study. The result implies that members of society have an occupation that varies in prestige. This is capitulated by Robert (2001) that some individuals have more access than others to higher-status-occupation, different level of educational attainment. And some have more access than others to better education, various economic recourses and different level of power to influence communities' institutions. Therefore, differences in the ability to control resources and participate in society's' rewards produce equal opportunities. Miller (2007) corresponds that they are less to perform well in school than other children from middle-class home.

Previous School Attended. Schools in this study are categorized into private and public schools. Private schools are independent schools, non-governmental, privately funded and are not administered by local, state or national governments. It is funded in whole or in part by charging their students for tuition, rather than relying on mandatory taxation through public funding. Public schools are a no-fee school, funded and operated by the state.

This is in connection with the claim of Estrada (2015), executive director of the Philippine Association of Private Schools and Colleges and Universities that many students from private schools are transferring to public schools, stating that one of the reasons is the rising cost of education and some of the parents cannot afford to send their children to private schools. It is noted that the operation of private schools depend on the tuition paid by the parents since there is no direct subsidy from the government.

In this study, it is indicated that 111 (64%) respondents graduated from public schools and 63 (36%) respondents are from private schools. With the results from the socioeconomic profile of the respondents, this is attributed to the fact that most of the respondents belong in a Class E socio-economic classification thus explains that they were sent to a public school.

Social Media Platforms

Social media offer preservice teachers a large network of mentors and colleagues who can help them translate theory into practice as they launch their new careers. These platforms include Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, MySpace and Snapchat. The proliferation of social media in the internet has gained popularity. Hence, Ellison (2007) deduced that these sites have attracted millions of users worldwide by providing a platform where people search for news, information, business and entertainment. Social media use allows users to create personal profiles, while connecting with other users of the sites. Users can upload photographs and post what

they are doing at any given time.

In this study, determining the different social media platforms being used is significant, for it provides data regarding the respondent's background on social media. Figure 1 depicts the various social media platforms that the respondents commonly use. It clearly indicates that almost all (70%) of the students have Facebook account and is using them. A detailed account of the respondent's choice of platforms is indicated in the Appendix E.

This result is attributed to the fact that there were 123 respondents who claimed to use Facebook. This implies that most of the students in the Teacher Education program have Facebook accounts. Nowadays, Facebook is easier to access even outside their house through smart phones. College students have easy and quick access to the web thus, they get engaged with it more and more. Teacher education students claimed using Facebook notably for peer-to-peer communication around the group work. One feature of Facebook is the Messenger which lets the respondents communicate with each other for free. As some may claim, "Facebook is easy to use and Messenger lets us communicate for free. You just need two things: a smartphone and a free data."

With this, social media use by undergraduate students reflects more on their academic grades. Morris (2011) also reveals that college students who utilize Facebook spend less time on studying and have lower grades than students who do not use the popular social media.

Pew Research Centre (2017) pointed out that Facebook is the most-widely used of the major social media platforms, and its user base is most broadly represented of the population as a whole. Facebook has become one of the major daily routines of people especially young adults. However, the graph shows 1% of the respondents do not use Facebook. Through an interview, few of the respondents reasoned that it is too mainstream and they would rather spend their time with other social media platforms such as Youtube. As these respondents assert, "Facebook is too mainstream and there are a lot of fake news and negativity." This implies that these respondents would choose other social media platforms rather than Facebook to gain legit information and maintain their privacy.

Aside from its easy access, Instagram is ranked second due to its unique features and is a popular visual social media site. In an interview, the respondents are attracted to its elegant style and filters. In spite of this, they are adept at using this for personal communication and entertainment purposes, but not in terms of educational usage as a strategic communication tool.

One of the reasons why Twitter has attracted 4% of the Teacher Education students is that it provides access to classmates and those in the same field with whom they would not normally interact in face-to-face settings.

Figure 1. *Social Media Platforms*

Frequency Of Social Media Platforms Usage

It is significant to determine the rate of which the respondents visit any social media platforms because this determines how frequent the students are exposed to it. In this study, the respondents are asked on how often they access to these platforms on a daily basis. Figure 2 presents the frequency of social media platform usage. A detailed account on the frequency of media use is attached in Appendix F. Data show that 127 (73%) respondents use these platforms from 1 to 5 hours. This entails that with the easy accessibility of social media platforms in smart phones, Teacher Education students can update accounts any time they want. In the interview, few responded that they would only spare a few minutes for these platforms however it later turns into hours. This is in comparison with the various studies toward figuring out why we're participating in social media, specifically Facebook. Seiter (2016) ascertains that when one get a positive feedback on Facebook, the feeling lights up this part of our brain. The greater the intensity of our Facebook use, the greater the reward. Facebook can evoke the feeling when one is engrossed in a project or new skill.

Filipinos spend more time on social media that anyone else in the world, according to a global study, solidifying the country's reputation as an online engagement hub. This is asserted by Camus (2018) that Filipinos would normally spend 9 hours and 29 minutes a day on

the internet, based on the 2018 report. This was the second-highest in the world after Thailand at 9 hours and 38 minutes.

Facts prove that it may be the case, however, the graph also shows that 4 (2%) respondents use these platforms for only 1-3 hours per day. This implies that respondents in the age range of 31-45 years old wherein they claim to have other responsibilities with their family and work that limits their media use. This is true with the Pivotal Research analysis of Nielsen data per Business Insider. The amount of time adults spent on Facebook declined 4% year-over-year in November 2017. Meanwhile, time spent by adults on Google platforms in November 2017 reached 28.6%, up 5 percentage points.

Figure 2. Respondent's Frequency of Social Media Platforms Usage

Spelling Skill Proficiency Level

Spelling skill proficiency level is determined as Independent/ Mastery, Instructional and Frustration Level in reference of Spinelli's ISI Spelling Skill Proficiency Level.

Results of the study shows that the proficiency level of the Teacher Education students is described as Frustration Level with a mean of 60.17241. This is due to the fact that 4 (2%) respondents belong to Independent Level, 22 (13%) respondents belong to Instructional Level and 148 (85%) respondents belong to Frustration Level.

With 174 respondents, only 4 (2%) acquired an average score of 91.5 and a score of 90%-100% which is categorized as Independent or Mastery Level. Few of these respondents belong to the Junior and Senior year of Teacher Education program. Through an interview with these respondents, it has been revealed that they are fond of reading books such as novels since their young age. Data implies that these respondents have mastered through constant practice and encounter of these words.

This is consistent with Foorman (2004) asserting that spelling and reading are closely linked, in the findings that children who are good readers are usually good spellers. Knowledge of a word's spelling almost always aids the reading of that word.

With that in view, Table 2 shows that 22 (13%) respondents obtained an average score of 80.45 and a score of 75%- 89% during the conduct of the study which is categorized as Instructional Level. Data entails that most of these respondents are those who reacted in the words' pronunciation. During the conduct of the study, IPA symbols were specified to pronounce the words accurately. However, the respondents claim that they have knowledge of the words and its meaning, but they were not aware of how it is pronounced accurately. Results imply that their claim is in consistent with the common words considered as their common difficulty.

This is true as Lanir (2011) defines spelling or orthography, as a neurologically demanding sub-skill of writing, involving a range of linguistic skills. Spelling proficiency requires the acquisition of phonological knowledge, morphological awareness, and orthographic rules. So, in order to spell, learners need to have control over the sounds and structure of a language and its spelling system. With the respondents' claim, it is a fact that half of all English words can be spelled accurately on the basis of sound-symbol correspondences alone, meaning that the letters used to spell these words predictably represent their sound patterns. These patterns are somewhat complex and must be learned.

With the 174 respondents, 148 (85%) respondents acquired an average score of 56.31 and the score below 75% which is categorized as Frustration Level. These numbers show that many of the words given are not yet mastered and encountered by the respondents. Most of the Teacher Education students claim that they lack practice and drills during their formative years. Through an interview, some of the respondents are not inclined with literature and were not motivated to read books. However, they also stress that they have encountered the words but were not aware of its accurate spelling and just relied on pronunciation. This result implies that there is a

need for remedial activities with these students due to the fact that good spelling is a necessary skill for both higher education and the workplace. Furthermore, Jayousi (2011) emphasizes that spelling difficulties cause learners to commit many spelling errors that distort their written production, affecting negatively their overall writing proficiency. With this, Smith (2015) concludes that spelling proficiency forms an integral part of the academic achievement.

It can be deduced that there are some factors to be considered such as the mindset and preparation of the respondents on the conduct of the study. It is then recommended for the respondents to undergo remedial action and activities to further enhance and develop their spelling skill proficiency level.

Table 2. Summary of Spelling Skill Proficiency Level

<i>Level</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total Score</i>	<i>Average Score</i>
1 (Independent/ Mastery)	4	2%	366	91.5
2 (Instructional)	22	13%	1770	80.45
3 (Frustration)	148	85%	8334	56.31
Total	174	100%	10470	60.17
Description	Frustration Level			

Common Errors In Spelling

Common words which were misspelled and are considered as errors in the study were determined through frequency counts which means that words misspelled by 100 or more by the respondents are regarded as common errors.

Table 3 shows the distribution of the common errors in spelling. Data entails that the common difficulties that the respondents encountered are those which they are confused with. The shared attribute that these words have is the pronunciation which has silent letters. Other spelling conventions that the students find difficult to spell are words classified as borrowed foreign languages in English. These words are not within the common spelling convention in English words when it comes to pronunciation and spelling.

Understanding the relationship between letters and their corresponding sounds is an important skill for successful spelling performance. Within the context of letter-sound correspondence, it allows students to identify the sounds that correspond to the written symbols or letters. For spelling, learners identify the written letters that correspond to the spoken sounds. Many words in the English language have regular phonemic patterns. Predictable patterns for regular words allow students to spell these words solely on the basis of their letter-sound relationships.

The spelling of words in English is more regular and pattern-based than commonly believed. These patterns, though, are somewhat complex and must be learned. Some of the English words would only have one error if they were spelled on the basis of sound-symbol correspondences alone which means that the spelling of most words is mostly predictable. Many more words could be spelled correctly if other information was taken into account, such as word meaning and word origin. It can be deduced with the result shown on Table 4 that there are certain types of words that the respondents commonly misspelled. These words fall into categories such as words with silent letters, doubling letters and foreign words borrowed in English language.

Silent Letters. During the conduct of the study, few of the respondents reacted to the pronunciation of these words claiming that they were not aware that some are pronounced that way. Spelling proficiency requires the acquisition of phonological knowledge, morphological awareness, and orthographic rules. So, in order to spell, learners need to have control over the sounds and structure of a language and its spelling system. This spelling convention emphasizes that letters in words that are not pronounced make a huge difference to the meaning and sometimes the pronunciation of the word. The students understanding their roles will definitely help them in proficiently writing the accurate spelling of the word. The words in this study include hiccough, diphthong, pseudonym, hemorrhage, liaison, caffeine, gauge, bankruptcy, crucifixion and colleague.

In many English words, the spelling is different from pronunciation. Mahapatra (2017) verifies this fact that this is mainly because pronunciation has changed the last few hundred years, while the spelling system has stayed more or less the same. Second language learners have serious problems in acquiring intelligible pronunciation in English, because of the existence of silent letters.

Doubling Letters. In English, when you want to change the form of a word, one of the main tools you have is the ability to add a suffix. A suffix is an extension added to the end of the word stem to change the meaning. For instance, in this study, words such as beginning, bizarre, millennium, and occurrence are categorized in this spelling convention. The respondents claim that they are confused as to the pattern of when to double the letters in the given word. Sometimes the spelling of a word changes when adding a suffix; letters get doubled, or a letter gets dropped.

The respondents' claim is verified by Treiman (2016) in which studies suggest that the phonological properties of the preceding vowel influence people's decisions about whether to spell a medial consonant with a singleton or a doublet. Choosing between alternative spellings for sounds can be difficult. People use the phonological route when spelling non-words and words whose spellings are not firmly stored in memory.

Foreign or Loan Words. As stipulated, the words used in this study to determine the common errors in spelling are taken from the

reference books of the Teacher Education students. This involves various disciplines of the respondents' specialization and subject matter including literature books. With the result shown on Table 3, it is evident that some words are categorized as foreign or loan word in English language. Respondents claim that it is the first time they encountered words such as grotesque, jalousie, and holocaust.

One reason for spelling irregularities in English is the fact that many foreign borrowings have brought foreign spelling conventions with them. Most of these words are borrowed from Latin, Greek and German languages. English is already established as the de facto lingua franca. Rao (2018) expressed that a great number of words have been borrowed into English language. It has the largest amount of vocabulary that makes the learners confused to understand its semantics, structure, grammar and pronunciation which verifies the respondents claim on this matter. The loan-words were influenced and changed their semantic, structural or more or less morphological meaning, even their phonetic appearance.

Through an interview, few respondents claim that having knowledge on the word's meaning is different with mastering its spelling which they take for granted. Some respondents insist that they were not aware of the words which have the same sounds yet different spelling.

It is conceivable that the poor performance of learners has left schools and teachers disenfranchised with the idea of teaching spelling skills directly. Additionally, the conventional wisdom regarding the written English language is that its spelling patterns is believed to be quite complex. Many English words are not spelled like they sound, or they have irregular spellings. Given this perception regarding the difficulties surrounding spelling, Dixon (2001) indicates that one should not wonder at the number of children and adults who reportedly have trouble with spelling. Results in this study imply that some words taken from the reference books from the Teacher Education students were not encountered and mastered by the respondents.

Table 3. Distribution of Respondent's Common Errors in Spelling

Word	IPA	No. of Respondents	%
1. hiccough	/ˈhɪkəp/	160	92
2. grotesque	/gruːˈtɛsk/	152	87
3. jalousie	/ʒaløʒi/	151	87
4. idiosyncrasy	/ɪdiːoʊˈsɪŋkrəsi/	148	85
5. aggravate	/ˈægrəˌveɪt/	141	81
6. diphthong	/ˈdɪfθɒŋ/	137	79
7. fluorescent	/fluːˈresənt/	137	79
8. bizarre	/bɪˈzɑːr/	136	78
9. bureaucratic	/bjʊərəˈkrætɪk/	134	77
10. holocaust	/hələˈkɒst/	133	76
11. pseudonym	/ˈsʊdəˌnɪm/	125	72
12. centennial	/senˈtɛniəl/	124	71
13. irresistible	/ɪrɪˈzɪstəbəl/	122	70
14. millennium	/mɪˈlɛniəm/	121	70
15. agitate	/ˈædʒəˌteɪt/	120	69
16. hemorrhage	/hɛməˈrɪdʒ/	116	67
17. liaison	/liˈeɪˌzɑːn/	113	65
18. threshold	/θrɛˈʃəʊld/	113	65
19. amiable	/əˈmiəbəl/	112	64
20. dysfunctional	/dɪˈsfʌŋkʃənəl/	112	64
21. aerial	/ˈɛəriəl/	111	64
22. occurrence	/əˈkɜːrəns/	111	64
23. caffeine	/kæˈfiːn/	106	61
24. chisel	/tʃɪzəl/	105	60
25. conceivable	/kənˈsiːvəbəl/	104	60
26. gauge	/geɪdʒ/	104	60
27. ambiguous	/æmˈbɪɡjuəs/	103	59
28. bankruptcy	/ˈbæŋkrəptsi/	103	59
29. crucifixion	/krʊsiˈfɪkʃən/	102	59
30. colleague	/kəlɪɡ/	100	57
31. tedious	/ˈtiːdiəs/	100	57

Significant Relationship Among Socio-Demographic Profile, Media Use And Spelling Proficiency Level

In this study, there are three variables being compared and these are the respondent's socio-demographic background, social media platforms used and spelling skill proficiency level. As shown in Table 4, it is evident that some factors being considered have a significant relationship with each other while other factors does not implicate any significant relationship.

Facebook & Instagram Users, Age and Proficiency Level

The p-value of each variable was computed using Chi-square test, T-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Results showing p-

values below 0.05 indicates that there is a significant relationship among the variables and computed data below 0.01 indicates that there is a high significance among the given variables.

In terms of socio-demographic profile, social media platforms and proficiency level, the results shows that there is a significant difference in spelling proficiency skills among FB & Instagram users across age of respondents for it has a computed p-value of 0.018. It entails that most of the Facebook and Instagram users are 16-20 years old and belongs to Frustration Level. The result implies that age and media use are significant factors in determining the proficiency level of the respondents which is classified as Frustration Level.

Technology allows students to research more and to keep in constant contact with teachers through Facebook and Instagram. This denotes that Facebook and Instagram are used due to its common features of easy accessibility in communication and good visuals. With the respondents' claim that their usage for these social media platforms are not solely for educational purposes, it thus affects their proficiency level.

Facebook, Twitter & Instagram Users, Age and Proficiency Level

With the computed p-value of 0.007, data show that respondents who use Facebook, Twitter and Instagram compared to their age have a high significant relationship across the proficiency level of the respondents.

This entails that most of the respondents who use these three platforms are aged 16-20 years old and belongs to Frustration Level. These three platforms are owned by the same company and it shows that their unique and easy features attract many of the respondents in this age range. However, it significantly affects their spelling skills as well especially with Twitter's feature of limiting what is posted for only 140 characters. In this view, Smith (2015) underscores the profundity of taking cognizance of the students' spelling especially in the light of modern technology and social networking sites.

Facebook, Twitter & Instagram Users and Mother's Occupation

The study presents many dynamics of family development that take place based on income, parent's occupation and previous school attended. Because backgrounds vary across families, our nation's educational system faces many unique challenges as it commits to providing equal opportunities to all students regardless of sociodemographic profiles. These factors will heavily impact a student's educational and technological opportunities.

With the computed p-value of 0.040, data show that respondents who use Facebook, Twitter and Instagram compared to the variable of mother's occupation has a significant relationship.

Data show that respondents who use Facebook, Twitter and Instagram compared to their age have significant relationship across the mother's occupation of the respondents. A detailed account is shown in Appendix N regarding the cross tabulation of social media platforms, mother's occupation and proficiency level.

The results indicate that more than half of the respondents' mothers are housewives. Through an interview, some respondents claim that they are living far from home and they may need to communicate with their mother most of the time for updates. Having a phone as a means of communication and with these three platforms which has easy accessibility and free features for communication, it is evident that they have accounts for each platform.

Table 4. Significant relationships between socio-demographic profile, social media use and spelling proficiency level

<i>Variables Compared</i>	<i>Valid Cases (n)</i>	<i>Degrees of Freedom</i>	<i>Chi-square Value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Significance</i>
FB & Instagram Users, Age and Proficiency Level	27	6	15.341	0.018	Significant
FB, Twitter & Instagram Users, Age and Proficiency Level	10	2	10.000	0.007	Highly Significant
FB, Twitter & Instagram Users and Occupation of Mother	10	4	10.000	0.040	Significant

Proposed Module Enhancing Spelling Skill Proficiency

Results of the study shows that Teacher Education students have the spelling skill proficiency of Frustration level. This can be compared to the study of Smith (2015) proving that student educators tend to overestimate their levels of spelling proficiency. The findings highlight the crucial focus of paying attention to spelling even at the tertiary level, especially in the light of the fact that student educators will be teaching the Foundation Phase learners how to spell once they are appointed as educators in the schools.

The stakeholders agreed that there is a need to step up its efforts in improving the teaching and learning of English, developing it as a vital skill of the workforce. Given the importance of spelling proficiency to academic success, researchers and educators must determine the most efficient and effective methods to teach spelling.

With the analyzed data, it implies that there is a need to improve the spelling rules awareness of the Teacher Education students

regarding pronunciations, doubling letters, silent letters, with words classified as borrowed foreign words in English and other spelling conventions.

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn from this study:

Most of the respondents are aged 16-20 years old which means that it falls within the normal age range of a college student in the Philippine Educational system. Most of the respondents were freshmen who were pioneering in the K to 12 curriculum. There are more female respondents than male which means that more female students are enrolling in the Teacher Education program at Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception. It can also be affirmed with their parents' occupation that most of students belong to Class E of socio-economic classification developed and proposed by Nielsen Admosphere. It verifies the fact that most of them studied at public schools in their basic education formation due to the fact that it is funded by the government. This result proves that most of the respondents belonged to low-income families, however, they still had access to smart phones and other gadgets which enables them to use social media platforms. The social media platform that the respondents mostly use is Facebook which knows no generation limits and respondents access these social media platforms 1-5 hours on a daily basis.

From the data gathered and analyzed through statistical computations as bases in the components in the problems and objectives of the study, the spelling proficiency of the respondents taking Teacher Education at Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception is classified as Frustration Level with the percentage mean of 60.17%. It can be seen in the result of the spelling drill that the most common error falls in the classification of words with different pronunciations.

With the hundred words provided, the results show the ten most frequent or common errors of the respondents. It is evident that the highest of 160 errors is from the word hiccough which has the same pronunciation with the word hiccup and is considered as the common spelling that the respondents have encountered. Other errors reveal that the respondents are mostly confused with words that have silent letters and doubling letters. There are also words that can be classified as borrowed foreign words of English that the respondents find difficult to spell.

The study also revealed that some of the variables compared such as the respondents' age, has a significant relationship among FB, and Instagram Users and their proficiency level. With this, users of the three platforms, FB, Twitter and Instagram shows a high significant relationship among the respondent's age and proficiency level. Results show that there is a significant relationship between FB, Twitter & Instagram Users and Occupation of Mother. This implies that these variables affect the spelling skill proficiency level of the students taking up Teacher Education program at Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception College Baybay Leyte Incorporated.

The following recommendations are presented as derived from the conclusions and findings of the study:

Make use of social media platforms in the teaching-learning process and in instruction since it is inevitable that most of the Teacher Education students use these platforms on a daily basis;

Supply more enrichment activities and remedial lessons to enrich and develop their knowledge about the basic rules and concepts of spelling the words. A proposed module enhancing the spelling skill proficiency of the students is to be made used for the students in Teacher Education program;

Conduct a spelling drill every start of the lesson to further develop the student's spelling and vocabulary skills;

Assess the students' performance through constructive criticism especially after the spelling drill activity; and

Conduct further studies on the topic through qualitative or quantitative research. It should look into the respondent's reasons in using these social media platforms and how it helps into their development in their English vocabulary skills.

References

- Abbasova, M. (2016). The Impact of Social Networks on Students' English Language In Azerbaijan. *International Multidisciplinary Scientific Conferences on Social Sciences and Arts*, At Albena, Bulgaria, Volume: 3
- Agichtein, E., Castillo, C., Donato, D., Gionis, A., & Mishne, G. (2008, February). Finding high-quality content in social media. In *Proceedings of the 2008 international conference on web search and data mining* (pp. 183-194). ACM.
- Anderson, Monica, & Smith, Aaron. (2018). Social Media Use in 2018. <http://www.pewinternet.org/2018/03/01/social-media-use-in-2018/#>
- Bongato, Penny (2014). Call-center program, House bills, DepEd initiatives for English Proficiency. <http://josecarilloforum.com/eduNteach.html>
- Bosiwah, Lawrence. (2015). Spelling Errors among Junior High School Students in the Cape Coast Metropolis. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/276180492_Spelling_Errors_among_Junior_High_School_Students_in_the_Cape_Coast

Metropolis

- Cabigon (2015). State of English in PH: Should we be concerned? <https://opinion.inquirer.net/90293/state-of-english-in-ph-should-we-be-concerned#ixzz5d7rfSR3F>
- Camus, Miguel. (2018). PH is world leader in social media usage. <http://business.inquirer.net/246015/ph-world-leader-social-media-usage>
- C.G.A. Smith (2015) How Well Do You Spell? Spelling Proficiency of Foundation Phase Student Educators, *International Journal of Educational Sciences*, 10:3, 381-390, DOI: 10.1080/09751122.2015.11890360
- Dale, M. (2010). Trends in the Age Composition of College and University Students and Graduates. <https://www150.statcan.gc.ca/n1/pub/81-004-x/2010005/article/11386-eng.htm>
- Davis III, C. H., Deil-Amen, R., Rios-Aguilar, C., & Gonzalez Canche, M. S. (2012). Social media in higher education: A literature review and research directions. report printed by the University of Arizona and Claremont Graduate University, 8.
- Dijck J. & T. Poell (2018). Social media platforms and education. In *The SAGE Handbook of Social Media*, 579-591, edited by Jean Burgess, Alice Marwick & Thomas Poell. London: Sage.
- Dilts, Robert. (2000). Social Media and its Changes on Student's Formal Writing. *Angelo State Undergraduate Research Journal*. 192-193
- Dlamini, Khanyie. (2017). The Role of Social Media in Education. <https://lcibs.co.uk/the-role-of-social-media-in-education/>
- Fischer, F. W., Shankweiler, D., & Liberman, I. Y. (1985). Spelling proficiency and sensitivity to word structure. *Journal of memory and language*, 24(4), 423-441.
- Foreign Loanwords and Loan Translations. (n.d.) *The Farlex Grammar Book*. (2016). <https://www.thefreedictionary.com/Foreign-Loanwords-and-Loan-Translations.htm>
- Guðmundsdóttir, A. (2017). Social media use and its connection to gender, self-esteem and anxiety https://skemman.is/bitstream/1946/28351/2/BS%20verkefni_Arnheidur_Gudmundsdottir.pdf on February 26, 2018
- Hernandez, Butch. (2018). Speak Well, Read Well, Write Well. <http://opinion.inquirer.net/36250/spell-well-read-well-write-well#ixzz5KFwv0lMD>
- Hodgkinson and Goldberg (2000). The Impact of Demographics in Education. *The Impact of Demographics in Education*" (2014). Honors Projects. 329. <http://scholarworks.gvsu.edu/honorsprojects/329>
- House of IT (2018). <https://houseofit.ph/understanding-social-media-in-the-philippines-a-year-end-report/> on February 27, 2018
- Jayousi, Mohannad. (2011). Spelling Errors of Arab Students: Types, Causes and Teachers' Responses. <https://dspace.aus.edu:8443/xmlui/handle/11073/2716>
- Johnson, M. (2013). The Relationship between Spelling Ability and Reading Fluency And Comprehension in Elementary Students. https://www.nmu.edu/education/sites/DrupalEducation/files/UserFiles/Johnson_Mandi_MP.pdf
- Lanir, Lesley. (2011). Exposure to Misspellings Confuses Spelling Proficiency. <https://www.decodedscience.org/exposure-to-misspellings-confuses-spelling-proficiency/6104>
- Lee, Kevan. (2014). The Proven Ideal Length of Every Tweet, Facebook Post, and Headline Online. <https://www.fastcompany.com/3028656/the-proven-ideal-length-of-every-tweet-facebook-post-and-headline-online>
- Lituanas, P. M., Jacobs, G. M., & Renandya, W. A. (2001). An investigation of extensive reading with remedial students in a Philippines secondary school. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 35(2), 217-225.
- McMillan, Liz. (2017). Social-ology 101: 73% of Teachers Think Social Media and Texting is Bad for Grammar and Spelling but Half Use It to Better Understand Students. <https://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/social-ology-101-73-of-teachers-think-social-media-and-texting-is-bad-for-grammar-and-spelling-but-half-use-it-to-better-understand-students-300511261.html>
- Ocal, Turkan, & Ehri, Linnea. (2017). Spelling ability in college students predicted by decoding, print exposure, and vocabulary. *Journal of College Reading and Learning*, 47(1), 58-74.
- Parcells, Frank E. (2015). Social Media Trends 2015. Austin Peay State University. *Journal of AP Communication*, 10-11.
- Porter Michael. (2003) Spelling Attitudes and Abilities of Secondary Students. Theses and Dissertations. Rowan University. Secondary Education and Teaching Commons. 1358
- Rose, Mike. (1985). The language of exclusion: Writing instruction at the university. *College English*, 47(4), 341-359.

- Snow, Marguerite & Brinton, Donna. (1988). Content-based language instruction: Investigating the effectiveness of the adjunct model. *TESOL quarterly*, 22(4), 553-574.
- Maina (2018) 20 Popular Social Media Sites Right Now. <https://smallbiztrends.com/2016/05/popular-social-media-sites.html>
- Magbanua (2016). *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, Volume 6, Issue 11, November 2016 548 ISSN 2250-3153 English Proficiency of College Students
- Mahapatra, B. (2017). The Problem of Silent Letters in ESL Teaching and Learning. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT)*. Volume 5, Issue 4 December 2017 | ISSN: 2320-2882. www.ijert.org 3032
- Maurer, E. (2017). Why are So Many Teachers Women? <https://www.womenshistory.org/articles/why-are-so-many-teachers-women>
- Meyrowitz, Joshua. (1998). Multiple media literacies. *Journal of communication*, 48(1), 96-108.
- Micheli (2016) Social networking sites and low-income teenagers: between opportunity and inequality, *Information, Communication & Society*, 19:5, 565-581, DOI: 10.1080/1369118X.2016.1139614
- Mudassir (2015). The Impact of Parents' Occupation on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Kuala Terengganu. *Multilingual Academic Journal of Education and Social Sciences*. 2015, Vol. 3, No. 1. ISSN: 2308-0876
- Rao, C. (2018). The Significance of the Words Borrowed Into English Language <file:///D:/Downloads/Drcsrar-WordsBorrowedIntoEnglishLanguage.pdf>
- Seiter, C. (2016). *The Secret Psychology of Facebook: Why We Like, Share, Comment and Keep Coming Back*. State of Social 2019 Report.
- Smith, CGA (2015). Spelling Proficiency of Foundation Phase Student Educators. Department of Educational Studies, Faculty of Humanities, Tut Soshanguve North, South Africa. 10(3): 381-390
- Tran, Kevin. (2018). Social platforms are most popular among 18- to 29-year-olds. <https://www.businessinsider.com/social-platforms-are-most-popular-among-18-to-29-year-olds-2018-3>
- Treiman, Rebecca. & Kessler, Brett. (2014). How children learn to write words. www.researchgate.net/publication/267028872_How_children_learn_to_write_words
- Treiman (2016). Graphotactics and spelling: Evidence from consonant doubling. Department of Psychological and Brain Sciences, Washington University in St. Louis, United States. https://pages.wustl.edu/files/pages/imce/treiman/treiman_boland_2017_jml.pdf
- Turkan Ocal & Linnea Ehri (2017) Spelling Ability in College Students Predicted by Decoding, Print Exposure, and Vocabulary, *Journal of College Reading and Learning*
- Veil, Shari, Buehner, Tara, & Palenchar, Michael. (2011). A work-in-process literature review: Incorporating social media in risk and crisis communication. *Journal of contingencies and crisis management*, 19(2), 110-122.

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